

LCE-07-2016-2017

Developing the next generation technologies of renewable electricity and heating/cooling

MOSAIC

MOdular high concentration SolAr Configuration

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Duration: 48 months

= Deliverable: D9.5=

Reference material for courses

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Responsible WP9: Fabrizio Perrotta, AMIRES

Responsible TL: Fabrizio Perrotta, AMIRES

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

MOSAIC

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22/11/2018	V0.1	Project Coordinator + Administrative coordinator
22/11/2018	V1.0	All partners, PO

Executive Summary

Besides the R&D progress, the important aspects for the consortium are training activities and active participations at conferences, workshops, and seminars, and training activities.

The target group for the training are especially CSP professionals and technicians. They will be identified by all consortium members based on their experience and collaborations. Well educated professionals in this domain are a prerequisite for a successful and effective usage of CSP power plants. A specific seminar on the applications of CST technologies developed in MOSAIC will be organised in the last year of the project. The decision of the organization of this workshop will be adopted during the project execution considering the intellectual property rights and the willingness of the owners and partners involved in MOSAIC module. MOSAIC concept will be proposed as an additional technology to be included in the “reference course on STE technologies” developed during the STAGE-STE project and it will be potential presented in a conjoint seminar with sister projects.

A set of conferences, workshops, and seminars in the CSP domain have been identified by partners at the beginning of the project to disseminate MOSAIC results at the CSP Community (CSP Professionals, industrial stakeholders, researchers, policy makers). During these events the representatives of the project will have the possibility to communicate the project’s scope and possible interaction and exchange with initiatives and projects in the CSP field community.

During the first two years of the MOSAIC project, Consortium has established a clear strategy to disseminate project outputs to the CSP professionals and industrial stakeholders by identifying the results to disseminate and exploit during the project lifespan. Reference Material Course is the highest dissemination materials developed from the Consortium in the first two years for the project. The main events where the first MOSAIC outputs and material courses have been presented are **SolarPaces2018** and **ASME Power and Energy 2018**.

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2. Content of Deliverable

The deliverable **D9.5 Reference material for courses** refers to the project outputs (knowledge and know-how) developed and disseminate during the MOSAIC in the first 24 months.

Two scientific publications and oral presentations has been identified as material course for the project (full presentations are available on the appendix):

- **Numerical Investigation of a Helical Receiver for a New Solar Bowl Based CSP Technology.** Authors: M. Cagnoli, I. Pagola Barrio, A. Peña Lapuente, M. Sanchez Gonzalez, L. Savoldi, C. Villasante, R. Zanino (Presented at ASME Power and Energy 2018 Conference)

In this paper the focus is on a multi-thread helix concept for the solar receiver, which was proposed for the prototype: several helical pipes are wound on a cylindrical envelope and exposed to the one-sided, concentrated solar heating, as well as to the environment. The aim of this work is an accurate evaluation of the convective heat losses from the hot receiver outer surface, affecting its thermal efficiency.

- **"MOSAIC", a new CSP plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost: Authors:** Cristóbal Villasante, Iñigo Pagola, Adrian Peña, Marcelino Sánchez, Aitor Olarra, Eneko Gomez-Acedo, Saioa Herrero (Presented at SolarPaces 2018 Conference)

This publication aimed to present to SolarPaces community the new CSP plant concept under development in MOSAIC. The corresponding paper will be published in the AIP conference proceedings (expected publishing date is June 2019). It is an "open access" indexed journal.

Paper Abstract: The MOSAIC project aims to develop a commercial CSP plant concept over 1GW nominal capacity. High nominal capacity is reached in a modular way, where each MOSAIC module delivers thermal energy to connected thermal energy storage systems that supply their energy to a high capacity power block (>1GW). This modular configuration significantly reduces the specific cost of the power block (€/MW installed).

Each MOSAIC module consists of an innovative fixed spherical mirror concentrator arranged in the form of a semi-Fresnel and a moving receiver driven by a low-cost cable tracking system. This configuration reduces the amount of moving parts of the entire system, lowering the cost of the solar field and keeping high concentration ratios. This will ensure high working temperatures and therefore high cycle efficiencies and cost-effective use of thermal storage systems.

Energy from the sun is collected, concentrated and transferred to the heat transfer fluid at module level, where, due to the modular concept, the distances from the solar concentrator to the receiver are much shorter than in typical solar tower technologies. As a result, energy collection efficiency is maximized, atmospheric attenuation is minimized, and precision requirements can be lowered.

All these technical benefits can contribute to a lower capital cost of the whole system, while ensuring efficiency and reliability. This therefore has a strong impact on the final cost of electricity production.

3. Conclusions

D9.5 Reference material for courses is the dissemination materials related to the project outputs from the Consortium in the first two years for the project. At the moment, the MOSAIC reference material courses are:

- *Numerical Investigation of a Helical Receiver for a New Solar Bowl Based CSP Technology.*
- *"MOSAIC", a new CSP plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost.*

Reference material for courses will be updated at the end of the project in order to include the final MOSAIC configuration, including partners learning experiences. Furthermore, it will be presented and spread up to the CSP community through participation at already identified events and the final MOSAIC conference.

4. Degree of Progress

The deliverable is to 100% fulfilled. An updated version of the reference materials *Final reference material for courses (D9.7)* will be published at the end of the project (M48) with all public knowledge and know-how developed in MOSAIC project and it will be presented to the CSP professionals and industrial stakeholders at the event planned at the end of the year.

5. Dissemination Level

The Deliverable D9.5 is public and therefore it will be available to download on the project's website, in CORDIS and on demand.

6. Appendix

In this section it is reported the oral presentations *Numerical Investigation of a Helical Receiver for a New Solar Bowl Based CSP Technology* (ASME 2018) and *MOSAIC, a new CSP plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost* (SolarPaces2018):

SolarPACES2018

Solar Power & Chemical Energy Systems

Oct 2-5, 2018 | Casablanca, Morocco

IK4 TEKNIKER
Research Alliance

CENER

ADItch

**MOSAIC: CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST
CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST**

Cristóbal Villasante | Casablanca, 3th October 2018

MOSAIC

A new **CSP** plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost

Motivation

Approach

Development

Results and discussion

Conclusions and future work

MOSAIC

A new **CSP** plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost

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MOTIVATION

GOAL

Achieve high concentration ratios at lower cost to reduce LCOE

- **Main costs in CSP are due to the solar field (mainly tracking)**
- **3D concentration is required to achieve:**
 - High concentration ratios
 - High temperatures and efficiencies
- **Modular systems can achieve high efficiencies at lower cost**
- **Fixed solar fields have great potential for cost reduction**
 - Spherical concentrators have been seldom studied

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

Certain challenges need to be overcome but it is worth exploring new ways to implement the concept of spherical concentrators

MOSAIC

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APPROACH

MOSAIC CONCEPT; FIXED SOLAR FIELD WITH FRESNEL HEMISPHERICAL CONCENTRATION

Characteristics of hemispherical concentrators:

- Spherical reflector
- Fixed mirror concept
- Linear receiver
- 3D concentration

Single tracking system
But huge civil works

Fresnel approach can be applied:

- A series of concentric spheres concentrates in a single line
- Easily adapted to any terrain shape

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

Raytracing for concentric spheres

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

APPROACH

HEMISPHERICAL REFLECTOR PLANTS

Previous experiences for the implementation of hemispherical concentrators

	Non-EU projects				EU Projects			
	Experience 1	Experience 2	Experience 3	Experience 4	Experience 5	Experience 6	Experience 7	Experience 8
Description	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector power plant	Hemispherical Fresnel reflector	Semi-Fresnel fixed reflector
Photograph								
Date	1970's	1970's	1990's	2000's	1980's	Late 1990's	Early 2000's	2004
Validation site	Crosbyton, TX, USA	Haifa, Israel	Auroville, India	Armenia	Marseilles, France Recife, Brazil	Republic of Crete	UK	No experimental validation
Size	19.7m diameter	10m diameter	15m diameter	Data not available	10m diameter	30m diameter 110kWt / 35kWe	Proof of concept	Theoretical design
HTF temp	Steam at 538 °C	Data not available	Steam	Air at 850°C	Data not available	Air at 850°C	-	-
Status	Decommissioned	Decommissioned	Still in operation	Not completed	Decommissioned	Decommissioned	-	Positive techno-economic analysis

APPROACH

RELEVANT REFERENCES

The most relevant references for the project

	Solar Projects			
	Experience 3	Experience 6	Experience 7	Experience 8
Description	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector power plant	Hemispherical Fresnel reflector	Semi-Fresnel fixed reflector
Photograph				
Date	1990's	Late 1990's	Early 2000's	2004
Validation site	Auroville, India	Republic of Crete	UK	No experimental validation
Size	15m diameter	30m diameter 110kWt / 35kWe	Proof of concept	Theoretical design
HTF temp	Steam	Air at 850°C	-	-
Status	Still in operation	Decommissioned	-	Positive techno-economic analysis

...

	Other possible inspirations	
	A	B
Description	Hemispherical radio-telescope	Hemispherical radio-telescope
Photograph		
Validation site	Arecibo, Puerto Rico	Guizhou, China
Size	305m diameter (5 arcsec accuracy)	500m diameter
Status	Working	Open

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

APPROACH

RELEVANT REFERENCES & SELECTED APPROACH

SELECTED APPROACH

Modular multi-bowl plant concept

Fixed hemispherical semi-Fresnel concentrators

Ad-hoc Tracking system

	Solar Projects			
	Experience 3	Experience 6	Experience 7	Experience 8
Description	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector power plant	Hemispherical Fresnel reflector	Semi-Fresnel fixed reflector
Photograph				
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	Other possible inspirations	
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Photograph		
Date		
Validation site	Arecibo, Puerto Rico	Guizhou, China
Size	305m diameter (5 arcsec accuracy)	500m diameter
HTF temp	N/A	N/A
Status	Working	Open

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

APPROACH

MOSAIC CONCEPT | INTENDED BENEFITS

Cost effective system:

- Fixed mirror concentrators (unique vs hundreds of tracking systems)
- No need for wiring
- Cheaper and easier to install and repair structures/mirrors:
 - Fixed at ground level (low wind forces)

High and progressive flux :

- 3D concentration but a single linear focus → linear receivers
- Progressive concentration allows for optimum receiver design (minimum losses)
- High temperatures and efficiencies
- Lower costs for storage system

Modular approach:

- Affordable investment required to validate/optimize the concept
- Suitable for distributed applications as well as large plants
- Cost-effective power blocks

APPROACH

MOSAIC CONCEPT | KEY CHALLENGES

Tough flux conditions:

- High and very uneven fluxes
- Limited flux control

A single tracking system per module but much more complicated:

- Mobile receiver at high temperature and under high fluxes
- Long displacements
- Feeding and dragging

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

MOSAIC

A new **CSP** plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost

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DEVELOPMENT TARGET LOCATIONS

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST
CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

MOSAIC concept can and have to be adapted to location conditions (latitude, type of soil, etc.)
Most interesting locations have been identified

DNI (kWh/m² year)
for populated areas

Populated areas
with DNI above
2000 kWh/m².year

DEVELOPMENT

SEMI-FRESNEL CHARACTERISTICS CONCENTRATOR GEOMETRY

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST
CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

Selected conditions:

- Latitude: 30.5° N
- DNI: 3348 kWh/m² (Clear sky)

Optimization Variables:

- θ : Tilt angle
- r_{ap} : Aperture radius
- R : Form radius of the inner disk
- R_{form} : Global form radius
- $incrR$: Increment in radius

- Receiver length and radius
- Workspace (azimuth & elevation)
- ...

DEVELOPMENT

SEMIFRESNEL CHARACTERISTICS

FLUX ON RECEIVER SURFACE

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

UNWRAPPED CYLINDER SURFACE

EXAMPLE

- R: 20m
- Receiver radius: 0.15m
- θ : 7.18°
- Central bowl + 3 rings

ACCUMULATED FLUX ALONG THE YEAR

DEVELOPMENT

SEMIFRESNEL CHARACTERISTICS

RECEIVER LENGTH OPTIMIZATION

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

Main flux characteristics:

- Uneven flux
- Ring contributions
- Flux only from R/2 to mirrors
- Low flux on the lowest section

Ratio of accumulated energy along the receiver (latitude=30.50°, Tilt angle=7.18°, Concentrator radius=20m, Rform=72.40m, IncrR=2.16m, Receiver radius=0.15m)

ACCUMULATED CONTRIBUTION ALONG THE RECEIVER

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CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

DEVELOPMENT

SEMIFRESNEL CHARACTERISTICS FLUX DISTRIBUTION VARIABILITY

21st of March

DEVELOPMENT

SEMIFRESNEL CHARACTERISTICS REFLECTOR SIZE/SHAPE OPTIMIZATION

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CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

$R = 20\text{m}$ $\theta = 7.18^\circ$ $rap = 20\text{m}$ $incrR = 2.16\text{m}$

Flux contribution from each mirror (kWh/m²-year)

Energy: 1205 MWh
Mirror area: 1627 m²
Solar field cost: 240 k€

Energy: 1176 MWh
Mirror area: 1000 m²
Solar field cost: 148 k€

ENERGY

-3%

COST

-38%

COST PER kWh

-37%

DEVELOPMENT

WORKSPACE OPTIMIZATION

AZIMUTH AND ELEVATION ANGLES TO BE REACHED & OPERATING-HOURS OF THE SYSTEM

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

Annual energy contribution per sun angle (Wh)

Daily flux distribution:

- Low energy available in the morning or evening
- The system should not operate below a certain energy threshold (thermal and parasitic losses)

Tracking system:

- Higher tracking requirements to reach extreme positions

A compromise between cost and energy define the Workspace

DEVELOPMENT

WORKSPACE OPTIMIZATION TRACKING SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Classical tripod systems are costly when large displacements are required

Parallel kinematics based on cables are proposed:

- Potential for cost reduction
- Large distances can be achieved
- Supporting structures can be shared

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

DEVELOPMENT

HOW MODULES COULD SHARE ELEMENTS

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

Plant view 1 module	Plant view 4 modules	Plant view 9 modules	Plant view N modules
<p>5 towers: 4 pulling towers + 1 supporting tower</p>	<p>13 towers: 9 pulling towers + 4 supporting towers</p>	<p>25 towers: 16 pulling towers + 9 supporting towers</p>	<p>$N + (\sqrt{N} + 1)^2$ towers: $(\sqrt{N} + 1)^2$ pulling towers + N supporting towers</p>

MOSAIC

A new **CSP** plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost

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DEVELOPMENT

CURRENT STATE OF DEVELOPMENT

Global design has been finished:

- Solar field optimized
- Tracking system suitable for large displacements
- Optimized receiver design

For additional information on receiver design process see poster B-45

Prototype under development:

- Detailed design is on-going
- Construction planned to begin in autumn

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

EXPECTED BEHAVIOUR OF THE VALIDATION PROTOTYPE

DEVELOPMENT

CURRENT STATE OF DEVELOPMENT

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

Key parameters

Optimized Module

Latitude= 30.5°

- 4 rings
- $R = 20m$
- Tilt angle= 7.18°
- $R_{form} = 72.4m$
- $incrR = 2.16m$
- Receiver $\varnothing = 0.3m$
- Receiver length= 6m
- 519 kW
- 1000 m² mirrors
- 1176 MWh
- Winter (>200 kW): 5.25h

Validation prototype

Latitude= 42.59°

- 4 rings
- $R = 15m$
- Tilt angle= 15°
- $R_{form} = 30.5m$
- $incrR = 1.3m$
- Receiver $\varnothing = 0.3m$
- Receiver length= 4.5m
- 317 kW
- 600 m² mirrors
- 710 MWh
- Winter (>115 kW): 4.5h

MOSAIC

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CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

A new concept of CSP with potential for cost reduction has been proposed

All required components have been designed:

- Solar field including tailored mirrors
 - Cost effective tracking system
 - Receiver and flexible hose
-

A prototype to validate the concept is nearly finished:

- Prototype construction phase will start in Nov. 2018
 - Testing phase will start in Spring 2019
 - Preliminary results will be shown in SOLARPACES 2019
-

The most promising cases for commercial applications (distributed and large plants) will be defined

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

MOSAIC: A NEW CSP PLANT CONCEPT FOR THE HIGHEST CONCENTRATION RATIOS AT THE LOWEST COST

This research was funded by the MOSAIC project “MOdular high concentration SolAr Configuration” within European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no 727402.

SolarPACES2018

Solar Power & Chemical Energy Systems

Oct 2-5, 2018 | Casablanca, Morocco

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Numerical Investigation of a Helical Receiver for a New CSP Concept Based on the Solar Bowl Technology

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3. IK4-Teckniker, Spain

This project has received funding from the European union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement N° 727402.

Outline

Solar Bowl Features:

- Fixed spherical mirror
- Tracking receiver (cylindrical shape)
- Sun radiation concentrated along a line

Pro and cons:

- Fixed mirrors → Cost saving
- Time change of the aperture area → Optical performance limiting factor

Previous experiences:

Description	Place	Date	Bowl diameter
Solar kitchen ¹	Auroville (India)	Late 1990s	15 m
Pilot plant ²	Crosbyton (Texas)	1980s	20 m

¹ J. Van Den Akker et al., Refocus 5 (2004) 26-29

² E.A. O'Hair et al., Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, 114 (1992) 272-274

FIXED MIRROR

<http://www.powerfromthesun.net/Book/chapter09/chapter09.html>

http://solarcooking.wikia.com/wiki/Auroville_Solar_Kitchen

Background (II): MOSAIC Project

Horizon 2020 project

Project goal:

Reduce LCOE for CSP by a non-tracking mirrors modular approach

- Global CAPEX reduction (low cost of the mirror field and receiver)
- OPEX reduction (simple tracking system and easy maintainability)

Innovative aspects

- Modular concept: easy to scale up
- Cost effective tracking system
- Cost effective semi-Fresnel not-tracking mirrors
- System designed to reach high concentration
- Linear receiver suitable for high and uneven heat fluxes

<http://mosaic-h2020.eu/>

Develop a thermal-hydraulic lumped-parameter model of the linear receiver

Optimize the receiver design parameters in terms of thermal performance

Prototype configuration

Start of the commissioning phase: late 2018

Site: close to Sangüesa (Spain)

Real module	Prototype
Molten salts	Thermal oil
Optimized bowl size	Reduced size

Linear receiver outer size (cylindrical shape)

- Diameter = 0.3 m → Optimized for the real module
- Height = 4.5 m (60% of R/2) → Little energy lost ($\approx 16\%$)

Analyzed Receiver Designs

ANNULAR

Laminar flow in the annular region → very poor thermal performance

EXTERNAL TUBES

Several complex U-junctions → serious drainage issue (molten salts)

HELICAL

No strong drawbacks
Already used in the Crosbyton pilot plant

Helical Receiver: Key Design Parameters

Bundle of parallel helical pipes

Key design parameters:

- Helix height ($L = 4.5\text{m}$)
- Helix diameter ($D = 0.3\text{m}$)
- **Pipe diameter (d)**
- **No. of parallel threads**

↓
Thermal-hydraulic analysis

↘
Optical analysis

- ❑ Mass flow evenly distributed among the parallel threads
- ❑ Adiabatic back side (well insulated)
- ❑ Adjacent pipes: no thermal coupling
- ❑ Negligible azimuthal conduction¹

¹ M. Rodriguez-Sanchez et al., Applied Thermal Engineering 63, 428-438 (2014).

Discretization: each parallel threads is divided in n control volumes

Modelica

Curvature taken into account by means of **suitable correlations** (friction¹ & inner HTC²)

Dynamic Mass & Energy balance + Steady Momentum balance

¹ J. Hart et al., Chemical Engineering Science 43, 775-783 (1988).
² T. Sobota, Developments in Heat Transfer, Chapter 16 (2011).
³ D.L. Siebers et al., Sandia National Laboratories Report, SAND 84-8717, 1984

Fixed parameters & materials

Parameter	Value
Receiver height	4.5 m
Helix diameter	0.3 m
Pipe wall thickness	1.5 mm
Surface coating	Pyromark 2500
Wall material	Incoloy 800

Pipe diameter & No. of threads changed parametrically

Heat Transfer fluid:
Thermal Oil (Helisol 5A)

Imposed inlet/outlet temperatures
Mass flow rate such to ensure the desired outlet temperature

Best or worst case

Only natural convection

Receiver orientation: vertical

Results

Impact of the flow direction on the receiver performance

Receiver axial position optimization on the base of the peak flux position

Parametric study: number of threads and inner pipe diameter

Parameter	Value
Pipe diameter	0.5 - 1 - 2"
Number of threads	1 - 2 - 3 - 5

Impact of the Flow Direction

Best flow direction: bottom \rightarrow top

Worst case scenario

Standard axial positioning of the receiver

Strongly non-monotonic temperature trend !

¹ Jung, Energy Procedia 69 (2015) 663 – 671

Receiver Axial Position: Optimization

Worst case scenario

Optimized axial positioning of the receiver

Almost monotonic temperature trend

NOTE: No adjustments required for the best case

pipe diameter = 1"
Imposed inlet/outlet Temperatures

$$\eta_{rec} = \frac{\text{power to fluid}}{\text{incident power}}$$

$$Re = \frac{4\dot{m}}{\pi d \mu}$$

- Increasing the No. of threads:
- Reduction of the **Reynolds number**
→ lower HTC → lower efficiency
 - + Reduction of the **pressure drop**
→ less power spent to circulate the oil

Power to overcome the $\Delta p \ll$ power gained due to the enthalpy increase ($\approx 10^3$ times)

The smaller the number of threads, the higher the efficiency

No. of threads = 3
Imposed inlet/outlet Temperatures

$$\eta_{rec} = \frac{\text{power to fluid}}{\text{incident power}}$$

- Increasing the pipe diameter:
- Reduction of the **Reynolds number**
→ lower HTC → lower efficiency
 - + Reduction of the **pressure drop**
→ less power spent to circulate the oil
- Power to overcome the $\Delta p \ll$ power gained due to the enthalpy increase ($\approx 10^3$ times)

$$Re = \frac{4\dot{m}}{\pi d \mu}$$

The smaller the pipe diameter, the higher the efficiency

Conclusions & Perspective

- Helical receiver configuration = most promising for solar bowl systems
- Flow direction strongly affects the temperature profile along the receiver due to the uneven heat flux distribution (bottom → top best choice)
- The receiver axial position must be optimized if the peak flux is far from the receiver top (outlet) side
- Thermal performance improves reducing the number of threads and the diameter of the pipes

Results still valid when moving to the real MOSAIC module (full size + molten salts)

In perspective:

- Model validation against experimental data (tests are planned on the prototype)
- Convective losses estimation using a CFD 3D model of the external air flow (wind)
- Thermo-Mechanic analysis starting from the computed wall temperature distribution

This project has received funding from the European union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement N° 727402.

